

Complications Associated with Pregnancy: Consequences of Advanced Maternal Age

Abstract:

In the recent century, the ratio of advanced maternal age women is rapidly increasing, especially in developed countries. Following this ratio, the need for comorbidities like diabetes, cholesterol, and hypertension, and fertility therapies are becoming common and the reason behind negative fetal and maternal outcomes. This review paper is based upon a detailed study of how advanced maternal age has negative consequences and why women, with age above 40, should be well aware about risks of complications during their pregnancies and delivery.

Keywords: Advanced maternal age; pregnancy, fertility therapies, negative outcomes, intrauterine fetal death, hypertension.

Introduction

Due to socioeconomic, educational, and social factors many women are delaying their childbirth. They delay their pregnancies up to a fourth and fifth decade and many of them are nulliparous at the time of delivery because in the developed countries women are more engaged with their professional career while most of those women in developing countries are multiparous. Elderly gravidas termed was used for women above age 35. Studies have shown women aged over 40 have shown more interest especially with the widespread use of assisted reproductive technologies. Many studies have reported that postmenopausal women above age 50 have pregnancies with egg donation. Because of their maternal and perinatal mortality, such women were discouraged a few years ago from getting pregnant. Meanwhile, some studies have shown a favorable outcome in such elderly pregnant women.

The study aimed to determine the frequency of adverse obstetrical outcomes in women 40 years or older in comparison with women 20 to 30 years old at our institution. The goal here is to

highlight negative impacts upon health and provide basic insight to females about their reproductive system which changes with age.

- **The Pervasiveness of Advanced Maternal Age:**

Women all around the globe are indulged in the trend of postponing their pregnancies. According to the survey conducted by the U.N. the mean age of women who bear child sharply decreased from 29.1 years in 1950 to 1955 to 27.5 years in 1990-1995. This level remained the same till 2015, and it rose high in rich states in the last 3 decades. For instance, in Europe, the mean age level rose from 26.5 in the 1980s to 29.4 in 2010- 2015. These studies are similar to the reports of the Economic Cooperation and Development Office. This rise is linked with the declined proportions of pregnancies in females in their 20s and the increased proportion of pregnancies in their late 30s. According to surveys, the percentage was observed as 8% in 2009 of first births in females with 35 years of age, this percentage rose sharply by 23 in 2014 which added a 9.1% pregnancy ratio all around the globe. Furthermore, a significant rise in the birth

ratio was observed among women of age 40 plus. According to a report of US health department, from 2006-007 to 2017, 4% rise in pregnancies was observed among women aged 25 to 29 years, 18% among 30 to 34 years of age, 5% for 35 plus, 8% for 40 to 44 years of age, and 26% among 45 to 54 years of age.¹⁸ This rise in delaying childbirth is due to changes in a social lifestyle, changes in priorities like education, careers, use of oral contraceptives, and better access to developed reproductive technologies (ART).

- **The Aftermath of AMA on Reproduction:**

Fertility has a direct link with age, as a women's age increases her fertility decreases. This decrease becomes prominent from age 35 to onwards, and this is due to declined quality and quantity of egg-bearing follicles (oocyte). Fecundability began to decrease more sharply at age 37 and above. Owing to this, females with age 35 or above have an increased demand for fertility services like ART who delayed childbirth due to some social factors or medical concerns. Furthermore, when there are medical health issues with women like poor egg quality, primary

ovary insufficiency, or declined ovarian reserve, then an option for oocyte donation is present. This method can even help menopausal or perimenopausal women to become pregnant.¹⁹

- **Complications in 1st Trimester: Consequences of Advanced Maternal Age**

Assisted reproductive techniques themselves pose a risk to ectopic pregnancy. With time more and more risk factors add up to the ability of women to conceive, like multiple partners, delayed oocyte transportation, tubal pathology, pelvic infections, smoking. These issues raise infertility risks to 8 times in women age above 35 years. About 80% of miscarriages in AMA females are owing to spontaneous abortions at a late age. One thing here is prominent that, professionals found that abortions are done in the late age impact AMA women, and abortions carried out in the previous history or aneuploidy do not significantly have much to do with the advanced age infertility. Moreover, issues do occur like the transfer of more or fewer chromosomes in the fetus which can cause Down syndrome, trisomy, or other euploidy. Many other congenital malformations and birth defects are linked with the advanced age of the mother. These all

changes are due to declined quality of follicles which need more hormonal stimulation for ovulation. In comparison to young mothers, babies born to women age 40 or above have 2 times more chances of developing heart issues, craniosynostosis, and esophageal atresia, even after taking care of bad habits like smoking, ART, and maintain optimum body weight.

- **Complications in Late Pregnancy: Consequences of Advanced Maternal Age**

Advanced maternal age has been found at higher risk of holding obstetrical complications encompassing severe morbidities and a rise in the mortality rate of both the mother and the fetus. According to the report of CDC, the mortality rate in Europe rose with the rise in the age of the mother, especially in females with age above 35. It was observed that 11 deaths out of 100,000 births were common due to hypertension and other similar issues in comparison to women with age equal to 34 or less than it. High blood pressure and other similar factors can cause pre-eclampsia in 4% general population and this percentage rises to in women age 40 years or above, and even rises higher to 35% in women over 50 years of age. Women above age 40 are 3 to 6

times highly susceptible to developing pre-gestational and gestational diabetes mellitus. Specifically speaking, the general population is prone to this diabetes mellitus at about 3 to 7%, 7 to 12% are women with age 40 years or above, and women with age 50 years or above are 31% prone to this disease. Another dangerous factor that adds up to the late pregnancy complications is placental abnormalities. Placental abruptions and Previa are likely to occur in advanced maternal-aged women due to hypertension and multiparity. Placenta previa is one of the most dangerous, and harmful abnormalities linked directly with the advanced maternal age. Nulliparous females with age above 40 years are at risk of placental previa 10 times higher than nulliparous females with age 20 to 29 years (however, the absolute risk is low, about 0.25 to 0.03% respectively).

- **Postpartum Complications and AMA:**

In the scientific field, advanced maternal age and its association with postpartum complications are less known. However, according to a report,²⁰ many issues like fever, hemorrhage, prolonged

hospitalization, and blood transfusion were observed in AMA women. This report also stated that a need was observed for the transfer of advanced age women to ICU, but limited data was present on it. It was found that the prevalence of postpartum hemorrhages might be owing to various comorbidities like gestation diabetes mellitus and hypertension. Another study was carried out encapsulating women of age between 15 and 54. Professionals found that thrombosis and hysterectomy were far more common among the age group of 45 to 54 than the younger females.

- **AMA and Chances of Twin Embryos:**

It has been found that there are some chances of the transfer of more than 1 embryo through ART into the females which can lead to pregnancies of multiples. Twins are seemed to be a common outcome in advanced age women as compared to young females with age below 35 and who are primiparas. Multiple reports have highlighted the postpartum and pregnancy

complications including high blood pressure, GDM, hemorrhages, and cesarean delivery, along with severe outcomes like low birth weight, preterm birth, neonatal ICU submission.

- **Psychological Impacts of AMA:**

The psychological impacts of prenatal and postnatal stages and their association with the women's age were studied in young as well as in advanced age females. It was observed that depression and stress in the postpartum stage were higher in females with age above 35 years, interestingly this occurrence of psychological impacts was delayed in comparison to young females. However, these psychological effects can be normalized with social activities and advantages. Advanced age females are good at adapting themselves to parenthood and changed lifestyle, they showed better parenting skills and social support. Moreover, some studies have also shown that children born to aged parents perform better at school in comparison to children born to young females, especially to age between 18 and 25.

- **Long Term Impacts and AMA:**

Jaffe et al ²¹ stated that mortality rates were greater in aged women (above 55) who had no child, and this rate linearly declined for parous females with advanced age. However, it was found that longevity was greatly influenced by parity and the impacts of advanced age on the first delivery of a child were unclear. Moreover, breast cancer was found as one of the reasons behind delayed pregnancy. According to the Nurses' Health Study, a comparative evaluation of nulliparous women and young women showed that chances of developing breast cancer were 5% higher, 10% lower, and 20% lower in females with age 35, 25, and 20 years respectively. Another study from Taiwan showed that females who become pregnant at an early young age are less prone to death from brain cancer, chronic renal failure, and colon cancer.

The rise of the trend among couples in developed countries to start their family and have children also affects the paternal age. In the US, the average percentage of the age of new fathers has become 40 and greater than 40, which is doubled since the '70s. from 2007 to 2016, more than

40 million live births in the US have demonstrated that not only maternal but also paternal advanced age has adverse neonatal outcomes. It was found to be associated with stillbirths, preterm births, cleft palate, musculoskeletal syndromes, retinoblastoma, severe lymphoblastic leukemia, and neurodevelopmental issues in the baby. It was also found linked with maternal's health and the development of GDM and preeclampsia.

Given below are the methods, results, and discussion of the study carried out:

Methods:

Female over age 40 years who had delivered their first baby was compared with women age early twenty to thirty years. A total of 300 women met the inclusion criteria and were recruited in the study. Cases and controls were matched for parity, (nulliparous to nulliparous and multiparous to multiparous). Nulliparous included women who had not previously delivered a viable fetus (>24 weeks of gestation). Multiparas included women who had at least one prior

pregnancy that progressed beyond 24 weeks of gestation, regardless of the actual parity number. Multiple gestations, with their inherent increased risk of adverse outcomes, were excluded.

Data analysis was performed using SPSS statistical program.

SPSS was used for data analysis, for comparison of means of continuous variables student's t-test was used. Chi-square was used to evaluate discrete variables. A p value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results:

The mean age of women above 40 was 42.1 ± 2.2 years compared with 25.6 ± 3.5 years in the control group. Assisted reproductive technology was used by 9.1% of women over age 40 whereas only 2.3% used it in the control group. Gravidity and parity were significantly higher in cases compared with controls. In the study group, the mean gestational age at delivery was significantly lower. Induction was required more in the study group as compared to the control

group. However, there was no statistical difference found in the rate of normal delivery and duration of labor. Inductions were done for a medical or obstetrical indication in 65.3% of cases versus 41.9% of controls. Cesarean delivery was significantly higher in cases compared to controls. The most frequent dictations for CS in cases and controls were prior CS, no reassuring fetal tracing, abnormal presentation, and arrest disorders, respectively. Moreover, In either group parity did not seem to affect the indication for CS.

A higher rate of pregnancy complications was associated with advanced maternal age including preterm delivery, gestational diabetes, preeclampsia, chronic hypertension, and uterine myomas compared with controls. There was one maternal death in the advanced maternal age group. There was a high number of IUFDs seen in the study group.

After excluding the 2 study patients who were having the IUFD occur intrapartum during termination for a prenatally diagnosed chromosomal abnormality (trisomy 21), the mean gestational age at intrauterine fetal death was 32.1 weeks in the study group versus 21.3 weeks in

the control group. All 4 fetal deaths in the control group occurred at 24 weeks' gestation while only (4/17) 24.0% of such deaths occurred at this gestational age in the cases. Of the remaining 13 IUFD, 8 did not have an identifiable risk factor (preeclampsia, diabetes, postdates, or prematurity). Multiparous cases had significantly higher rates of preterm delivery, CS, preeclampsia, gestational diabetes, chronic hypertension, and labor induction compared with multiparous controls. However, only preterm delivery, CS rates, and uterine fibroids were found to be significantly higher in nulliparous cases compared with younger nulliparas.

Statistical difference was observed in perinatal outcomes was a higher rate of IUFD in multiparous cases compared with multiparous controls despite similar birth weights, rates of depressed newborns, and congenital malformations. The results of the multiple stepwise regression analysis are explained. Parity was not found to have a significant impact on the variables analyzed. Moreover, for obstetrical complications, the OR was 7.0 for patients who had

preexisting medical complications (hypertension, anemia, thyroid disorders, cardiac diseases, renal disorders, diabetes), while the OR for obstetrical complications was 2.1 in women over 40.

Discussion:

Until recently, advanced maternal age was considered one of the risk factors for an adverse maternal and perinatal outcome. Literature has reported more favorable outcomes for women in developed countries for delaying their childbirth because of many reasons. In developing countries, pregnancies above 40 are, in most cases, just a continuation of the reproductive life of these women. This study is one of the largest to compare a group of women at least 40 years old, to a matched group, aged 20 to 30, who are usually considered to have the lowest maternal and perinatal morbidity and mortality. In the current study, 83% of women presented who were multiparous, a rate similar to reports from the same region.

Despite controlling for parity, the mean parity was significantly higher in elderly women compared with controls. This is because multiparity was defined as at least one previous pregnancy that has reached the viability stage, not taking into account the actual parity number. In the case group, 65.7% of medical or obstetrical indications accounted for labor inductions whereas there was only 49.1% in the control group. A higher incidence of labor induction was seen more in the study group as compared to the control group. In elderly pregnant women, pregnancy complications were seen high as compared to the control group. In older women, Preterm deliveries were twice as common. The difference in preterm delivery rate remained significantly higher in cases even after excluding patients with medical or obstetrical indications for induction (11.3 vs. 4.6%), indicating an inherently increased risk for spontaneous preterm labor in elderly women. The incidence of gestational diabetes, preeclampsia, and chronic hypertension were also higher in the cases. Thus, the higher incidence of gestational diabetes observed in elderly women is not secondary to understating the incidence in the younger women.

The reasons for this increased frequency of complications vary according to the complication. As affected by age chronic hypertension and gestational diabetes are easier to explain. Moreover, preeclampsia is reported to be more frequent at the extremes of reproductive age. In our series, preeclampsia, chronic hypertension, and gestational diabetes were more frequent in multiparous elderly women compared with multiparous controls. This did not hold for nulliparas. The cesarean section rate was 2.5 times higher in our study groups compared with controls and this was true for both nulliparous and multiparous patients. This has been reported in virtually all studies. The most frequent indications in both groups were repeat CS, followed by nonreassuring fetal tracing, and abnormal presentation. However, the chance of delivering by CS was almost doubled for any indication in cases compared with controls. In some studies, the incidence of abnormal labor is higher in older patients, the basis of which is not clear. It was not demonstrable in our study. The presence of a higher rate of obstetrical complications and chronic medical illnesses in the study group might have contributed indirectly to the higher incidence of CS. These patients are more likely to have elective repeat CS and abnormal fetal heart tracings.

Although 15.2% of cases had cesarean delivery for a nonreassuring fetal heart tracing compared with 14.3% in controls, there was no difference in the percentage of Apgar score <7 at 5 minutes in both groups which might be explained by the fact that physicians might have a lower threshold to perform a CS in this group of patients with a “precious pregnancy.” This might have been a contributing factor to the rather high incidence of cesarean delivery in cases knowing that the average rate of primary CS is 14.4% while the rate of total CS is about 23.1% at our institution. The perinatal outcome was also significantly affected by age.

Although the incidence of intrauterine growth restriction was similar in both groups in our series, older women had a higher incidence of intrauterine fetal death and infants with Apgar scores <7 at 5 minutes. Even after excluding the 4 cases of fetal death occurring 24 weeks’ gestation and the 5 cases in which there was an identifiable risk factor for fetal death, 61.5% of cases of IUFD occurred without an identifiable risk factor in the advanced maternal age group versus none in the controls. If this is reproduced in other studies, then routine antenatal fetal heart resting might

have to be recommended in pregnant women at age 40 or more. This increased risk has been reported in some, but not all previous studies. The higher incidence of medical and obstetrical complications might explain some, but not all, cases of intrauterine fetal death. Congenital malformations were diagnosed antenatally in most of the cases and were found to be similar in cases and controls. Both minor and major anomalies, defined as anomalies that had a major impact on neonatal morbidity or mortality such as polycystic kidney disease, were included. Only a minor anomaly (cleft lip) was incidentally found in 1/17 of all the intrauterine fetal deaths that occurred in the elderly group. Thus, congenital anomalies were not a major contributor to the higher incidence of fetal death seen in the cases. In some studies, the incidence of chromosomal abnormalities was similar in elderly and younger women, and this was attributed to the aggressive prenatal genetic counseling and screening that these women have in developed countries. In our population, the acceptance rate of prenatal diagnosis is low especially in the young population and this might explain why the 3 cases of chromosomal abnormalities were seen in the advanced maternal age group (0.9%). Furthermore, the results of the multiple

regression analysis emphasized the importance of each variable in terms of the outcome. It is evident that as far as the high CS rate and the preterm delivery, age, and obstetrical complications are more important than parity.

Despite many limitations of this study, the data has enabled to discover multiple variables that significantly impact the maternal and fetal health like medical comorbidities and natural risk factors. This prospective not only aids women to know more about their reproductive system, but also provides them an insight to how and when get pregnant in order to avoid these complications. A large proportion of women were examined, thus enough data was obtained to find out differences between girls (15-19 years), young women (20-29), and older women (35-39 years and above 40). The deep research has highlighted complications of pregnancy and delivery that are linked purely with the women of advanced maternal age. On the basis of these findings, it is encouraged to proactively communicate these risks to women contemplating or delaying pregnancy or who already are pregnant. It is quite imperative for a woman to fully

understand all the possible risks of complications about pregnancy given their advanced age. In the nut shell, a woman should be well aware and able to communicate all the signs and symptoms she come across while trying to conceive or during pregnancy to her physician to avoid any future issues.

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